

ANALYSIS OF SHORT TRACK SPEED SKATERS COURAGE LEVELS FROM DIFFERENT VARIABLESⁱ

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Abstract:

The object of this work is to analyze the courage levels of short track speed skaters from different variables. The study has been carried out on a total of 20 individuals, including 6 women and 14 men, who performed as short track speed skaters in Erzurum province of Turkey in 2017. DBA courage scale developed by (Imamoğlu, 1998) has been applied to skaters in the study⁹. SPSS 21 package program has been used for the analysis of the data. In the analysis of the data, frequency distribution for the demographic characteristics, T test to examine the relationship between two independent variables and courage level and ANOVA Variance analysis tests have been used to examine the relationship between more than two variables and courage level. The difference between the variables has been interpreted based on p 0.05 relevance level. According to the findings, it is determined that there is a significant difference between the level of courage of the athletes and being a national athlete. It is also determined that there is no significant difference between gender, education level, age, type of school they attended, educational background of mother and father and mother and father's occupations. It is observed that, courage levels of national athletes are higher than that of non-national athletes. It is proposed that, it is important to determine the variables that will positively influence the level of courage for the athletes to be successful in sports and daily life.

Keywords: courage, short track skating, courage in sports

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1. Introduction

As is the case in many other sports branches, important developments are conducted in international scale in ice sports, the number of athletes are increased, more technological equipment are used and competition tracks.

Significant national and international competitions are held for various ice sports, both open and indoor. The short track (ice-skating) sport is one such competition and it is known that it originated in the Flemish countries in the 13th century. The short track sport based on competition is known to begin on frozen canals and lakes in 19th century Europe. Regularly held international competitions began to take place in the late 19th century and were included in the first winter Olympic games of 1924^{6,7}.

The short track, a sport in which female athletes or male athletes exhibit a rhythmical and powerful skating on a track of ice in an oval structure, is an important ice sport in the framework of the ISU International Skating Association competition program established in the Netherlands in 1892¹¹.

Today, short track contests are held in three different classes, long lanes, short lanes and marathons. As in many other competitions, it requires the skills such as strength, speed, durability, flexibility mobility, courage, coordination, balance, attention, self-confidence, fighting the whole self that are essential in success.

In the age we live, being courageous, self-confident, and able to demonstrate the necessary struggle with the whole self is an important factor in our success not only in sports but also in every other field. Athletes desire to be able to put their own self and courage together at the best level by using all the technical, tactical and competition rules that they have earned in their struggle to achieve success during the competitions. The athletes who believe in themselves, embrace their courage, absorb their ambition of persevere and self-confidence for their great struggle, have always succeeded in the Short Track sport as in all other sport branches.

Among the characteristics that athletes must possess in order to survive in the face of the obstacles they encounter and to reach their goals are the feelings of courage and self-confidence².

According to Corlett (2002), the concept of courage, known as a part of virtuous life, is neither a virtue nor a goal for perfect character. It is just a tool that will provide talent and benefit. Courageous actions have been co-managed with success⁸. Athletes must act courageously with the determination of perseverance and sportiness in the awareness of their abilities to reach their goals. They should be able to progress in the face of difficulties¹⁰. If an athlete tries to make a strong and bold struggle in the direction of talent and skills by performing preliminary preparations before and during the competition and at a strong level, success will also be achieved at such an effective level.

Individual's feeling of self-confidence forms concepts such as self-love, awareness of values and abilities, definition of feelings, and reconciliation with himself⁸. Lack of self-confidence leads to passivity, doubt, insecurity, depression and inferiority.

Therefore, no matter what the individual does, he/she must have a sufficient level of confidence to succeed and achieve his/her goals².

Internal confidence, on the other hand, includes feelings of self-esteem, self-love and recognition, and reconciliation with oneself. What reflects these feelings to the environment through attitudes and behaviours is the external confidence⁵.

Athletes with high self-confidence are individuals who think positive, are able to control their anxieties, succeed in being calm even under stress and focus on their goals⁴.

2. Materials and Methods

The purpose of this research is to examine the athletes' courage levels in terms of different variables. This study was carried out on a total of 20 example short track athletes, including 6 women and 14 men in the age range of 14 – 17 in Erzurum province of Turkey, in 2017.

The independent variables used in the research were prepared by the researcher. The DBA courage scale developed by Imamoğlu (1998) was used to determine the level of courage of individuals. The data of the study consisted of 12 items of "DBA courage scale" in which the athletes' DBA courage scale was evaluated. According to this, the lowest score obtained from the scale is 12 the highest total score 84 and the high score indicates that the level of courage is high⁹.

In the analysis of the data, frequency distribution to determine the demographic characteristics, T test to examine the relation between two independent variables, Anova analysis of variance tests were applied to examine the relation between two variables. The LSD test was used to determine the group from which the differences originated. All these tests were analysed in the SPSS 21 package program and the level of significance was taken as $p < 0,05$. Alpha value was found as 0,708 in the analysis of validity and reliability.

3. Findings

In this section, the analysis results for frequency distributions of demographic characteristics of short track athletes, who participated to the study, Independent-Samples T test analysis results to determine the relationship between two independent variables and courage level, independent- Samples T test analysis results to determine the relationship between two independent variables and courage level and one-way ANOVA test analysis results to determine the relationship between more than two variables and courage level are given.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Athletes Participating in the Study

Variable		Number (N)	Percentage (%)	Total Percentage (%)
Sex	Women	6	30,0	30,0
	Men	14	70,0	100,0
	Total	20	100,0	
Age	13	4	20,0	20,0
	14	4	20,0	40,0
	15	7	35,0	75,0
	16	3	15,0	90,0
	17	2	10,0	100,0
Education status	High School	18	90,0	90,0
	Elementary School	2	10,0	100,0
Type of School They Attend	Sports High School	12	60,0	60,0
	Elementary School	5	25,0	85,0
	Anatolian High School	3	15,0	100,0
Are you a National Athlete?	Yes	13	65,0	65,0
	No	7	35,0	100,0

The research was carried out on a total of 20 short track athletes including 6 women and 14 men and it is observed that 13 athletes are 13 national athletes and 7 athletes are not national athletes. The age distribution of the athletes is in the age range of 14-17 years and 18 athletes are in high school and 2 athletes are in elementary education.

Table 2: Family Characteristics of the Athletes Participating at the Study

Variable		Number (N)	Percentage (%)	Total Percentage (%)
Mother Education Level	Elementary School	13	65,0	65,0
	High School	7	35,0	100,0
Father Education Level	Elementary School	13	65,0	65,0
	High School	5	25,0	90,0
	University	2	10,0	100,0
Mother Occupation	Housewife	20	100,0	100,0
Father Occupation	Tradesman	10	50,0	50,0
	Self-employment	7	35,0	85,0
	Civil servant	3	15,0	100,0

When the family characteristics of the athletes participating in the research are examined, it is observed that the education level of the parents is mainly elementary education. In the distribution of the mother and father occupation, it is observed that all of the mothers are housewives and fathers are mainly tradesmen.

Table 3: Average and Standard Deviations of Points Scored by Female and Male Athletes at the Courage Scale and t Values of Differences between the Averages

Sex	N	X	Ss	t	p
Female	6	62,1667	13,97736	1,340	,145
Male	14	55,0714	9,37644	1,138	

It was found that there was no significant difference in P; 0.05 between the averages of the scores of male and female athletes.

Table 4: Average of Points Scored by Athletes' Level of Learning and Courage Scale and Values of Standard Deviations with t Values of Differences between Averages

Education Level	N	X	Ss	t	p
High School	18	58,5000	10,61215	1,644	,118
Elementary School	2	45,5000	10,60660	1,644	

It was found that there was no significant difference between the athletes' level of education and the average of the scores they got from courage scale at P; 0.05 level. Although not meaningful, it is observed that the level of courage of the athletes at high school level is higher than that of primary school athletes.

Table 5: Athletes' Status of National Athletes with Average of Courage Score Scores and Values of Standard Deviations with t Values of Differences between Averages

National Athlete	N	X	Ss	t	p
Yes	13	60,9231	11,50697	2,259	,034*
No	7	50,2857	6,15668	2,693	

It was determined that there was a significant difference in the level of P; 0,05 between the athletes' being national athletes and the average scores of the courage scale. It is observed that the level of courage of national athletes is higher than that of non-national athletes.

Table 6: Average Values of Athletes' Mothers' Training Levels and Courage Scores and t Values of Standard Deviations and Differences between Averages

Mother Education Level	N	X	Ss	t	p
Elementary School	13	57,5385	12,89454	,181	,858
High School	7	56,5714	7,43544	,213	

It was determined that there was no significant difference in the level of P; 0.05 among the athletes' mothers' level of education and the average of the points they got from courage scale.

Table 7: Values of Averages Difference between Standard Deviations and Averages of Points Scored by Athletes Age and Courage Scale

Age	N	X	Ss	f	P	Difference
13	4	56,2500	5,25198	,528	,717	-----
14	4	54,0000	12,54326			
15	7	56,1429	10,51077			
16	3	66,0000	14,73092			
17	2	56,0000	19,79899			
Total	20	57,2000	11,07677			

It was found that there was no significant difference in the P; 0.05 level between the averages of the points that the athletes of different age levels received from courage scale.

Table 8: Values of the Differences between the Average and Standard Deviations of the Points Scored by the Athletes at School Type and Courage Scale and the Differences between the Average

School Type	N	X	Ss	f	P	Difference
Sports High School	12	60,2500	12,16646	1,216	,321	-----
Elementary School	5	53,6000	9,65919			
Anatolian High School	3	51,0000	4,35890			
Total	20	57,2000	11,07677			

It was found that there was no significant difference in the P 0.05 level between the athletes' school type and the average of the scores they got from courage scale.

Table 9: Values of Average Difference between Standard Deviations and Averages of Points Scored by Athletes in the Levels of Courage and Father Education Levels

Father Education Level	N	X	Ss	f	P	Difference
Elementary School	13	58,6923	11,82782	,360	,703	-----
High School	5	53,6000	10,54988			
University	2	56,5000	10,60660			
Total	20	57,2000	11,07677			

It was found that there was no significant difference in the level of P 0.05 among the athletes' fathers' level of education and the average of the scores they got from courage scale.

Table 10: Values of Average Difference between Standard Deviations and Averages of Points Scored by Athletes from Their Father's Occupation and Courage Scale

Father Occupation	N	X	Ss	f	P	Difference
Tradesmen	10	57,0000	10,76001	,270	,767	-----
Self Employed	7	59,1429	11,88036			
Civil Cervant	3	53,3333	13,61372			
Total	20	57,2000	11,07677			

It was found that there was no significant difference in the level of P; 0.05 between the athletes' average scores of their father's profession and courage scale.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The aim of this study is to examine the courage levels of short track athletes from different variables. The study was carried out on a total of 20 short track athletes, 6 females and 14 males, and 13 of these athletes were national athletes and 7 athletes were not national athletes. The age range of the athletes is between 14-17 years. 18 athletes mentioned they are studying in elementary schools while 2 mentioned that they are in

high schools. It was found that there was no significant difference in $P; 0.05$ between the averages of the scores in courage scale of male and female athletes. Although there were no significant differences, it was seen that the average scores of female subjects were higher than male individuals. Can and Kaçay (2016) did not find a meaningful result in studying the relationship between athletic identity perception and courage and self-confidence in the study they conducted².

It was found that there was no significant difference between the athletes' level of education and the average of the scores they got from courage scale at $P; 0.05$ level. Although not meaningful, it is observed that the level of courage of athletes at high school level is higher than that of primary school athletes. It was determined that there was a significant difference in the level of $P; 0,05$ between the athletes' being national athletes and the average scores of the courage scale. It is observed that the level of courage of national athletes is higher than that of non-national athletes. It was found that there was no significant difference in the level of $P 0,05$ between the level of education of the parents and the scores of fathers' occupation and the courage scale. Doğru (2017), in his study, has found parallel findings to our study³.

It was found that there was no significant difference in $P; 0.05$ between the averages of the scores of the athletes of different ages at the courage scale. Can and Kaçay (2016) did not find a significant difference in their study². The result of this study is in parallel with the result of our study. It was found that there was no significant difference in the level of $P; 0.05$ among the averages of the scores of the athletes' school type and the courage scale. In a study conducted by Bostancı et al. (2016), there was no significant difference in the study of self-confidence levels of the students studying at the School of Physical Education and Sports¹. This result is similar to our study.

In order for athletes to be more successful in their sportive environment and daily life, it is necessary to determine the variables that affirm sportive courage, sense of athlete identity and self-confidence in a broader frame. In order for athletes to be more successful in their sportive environment and daily life, it is necessary to determine the variables that affirm sportive courage, sense of athlete identity and self-confidence in a broader frame. In order to increase the level of success and employment of athletes for each sports branch, the number of athletes, clubbing and schooling activities should be given more emphasis within educational and sportive aspects.

In sports where courage is important, choosing an athlete must first be guided by determining the levels of courage and by ensuring the support of coaches, sports trainers and managers.

In addition, it will be an important impetus to be able to place more emphasis on activities to ensure that they are sufficiently satisfied with their active sporting lives in parallel with their work on the expected sporting success of the athletes.

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